

BLENDED LEARNING APPROACH AND READING PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 4 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

One of the strategies supported by the BE-LCP is blended learning (BL), also known as mixed-mode education or hybrid learning, which refers to combining one or two distinct learning approaches with more traditional teaching methodologies. Yet, there were gaps in reading among students based on results in international and local assessments. On this premise, this study determined the relationship between the blended learning approach and the reading performance of the Grade 4 students in the District of Tarangnan, Schools Division of Samar, during the School Year 2022-2023. Using the descriptive-correlational research design, this study involved 266 Grade 4 students from the different public elementary schools in the District of Tarangnan, Schools Division of Samar. The study revealed that the median age was 10 years with a moderate MAD of 1.7 years; a higher representation of female students at 58.27 percent compared to male students at 41.73 percent; the largest group of student-respondents had parents who were high school graduates (28.95 percent), followed by college graduates (19.17 percent) and elementary graduates (20.30 percent); 18.42 percent of student-respondents had employed parents, while 81.58 percent have unemployed parents; came from lower-income families, with 34.59 percent falling in the Php 1,000.00 - Php 5,000.00 range; majority or 96.99 percent, had a normal nutritional status, indicating overall satisfactory well-being; majority or 88.35 percent had access to books at home. Moreover, the grand weighted mean of 4.16 suggested that students had a positive attitude toward schooling. Additionally, the reading performance in Filipino of the student-respondents indicated a scoring range of 16-20, with a median score of 15, and a 15-19 range of score, with a median score of 15 for English, which are both reflective of high levels of reading performance. The study likewise found that the blended learning approach effectively enhanced the student-respondents' level of reading performance

in terms of comprehension, reading, and speed. Finally, the study showed that the parents' highest educational attainment and their attitude toward schooling were significantly related to their reading performance in English and Filipino, and reading performance level in a blended learning approach.

Keywords: *Blended Learning Approach, Reading Performance, Comprehension, Reading, Speed*

INTRODUCTION

In a country such as the Philippines, where English is regarded as a second language, students' capacity to attain high reading performance levels has long been a major educational concern (OECD, 2019). Reading is widely recognized as a gateway to learning across multiple disciplines; hence, the development of strong reading skills at the elementary level is considered fundamental to overall academic success (Duke & Cartwright, 2021). Despite this, many students experience significant difficulties in reading and interpreting English-language texts, challenges that are further compounded in second-language learning contexts and thus require urgent attention from education policymakers (OECD, 2019). To address this persistent concern, the implementation of innovative teaching and learning approaches, such as blended learning, has been proposed as a means of providing more individualized and flexible learning experiences. Studies have shown that blended learning can positively support English as a Second Language (ESL) learners by enhancing engagement and improving reading performance when appropriately designed and implemented (Adling, 2022; Rahimzadeh & Gilakjani, 2022).

Educational policymakers must quickly develop solutions to prevent, or at least lessen, the effects of certain societal conditions and guarantee the students' continuous education. In light of this, the Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD) has investigated how its member countries responded to the demand for continuous learning of students amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. The reduction of in-person interactions in schools was the most practical and quick solution implemented by the majority of the countries, which brought on attention to the use of alternative learning delivery modalities beyond the school grounds. However, the OECD countries provide online learning the least amount of support due to the lack of technological infrastructure, which, on average was only nine percent of students worldwide have a quiet area to study at home, whereas over 30 percent of students in the Philippines have such spaces (OECD, 2020).

In the face of the COVID-19 pandemic, the Philippines has formulated the Basic Education-Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP), that was legally mandated by virtue of the Republic Act Number 11494, which was also known as the "Bayanihan to Recover as One Act". The BE-LCP has become a legitimate framework, which has allowed basic education students to continue their education and for teachers to provide instruction in a safe work and learning environment. The Department of Education (DepEd) has specifically responded by streamlining the competencies in the K to 12 Curriculum to

the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in the BE-LCP, and has promoted the development of remote learning delivery approaches like blended learning through DepEd Order Number 12, Series of 2020 or also known as the “Adoption of the Basic Education-Learning Continuity Plan for School Year 2020-2021” (DepEd, 2020).

One of the strategies supported by the BE-LCP is blended learning (BL), which is not a revolutionary approach in the country’s educational system. In 2007, the country implemented blended learning as a youth after-school program. As a result, it is not a novel method of delivering education in the country. This approach is also known as mixed-mode education or hybrid learning. It essentially refers to combining one or two distinct learning approaches with more traditional teaching methodologies. For example, carefully balancing online and in-person learning experiences in the classroom can promote teamwork and facilitate convergence of technologically-advanced environments with more traditional ones (Platonova et al., 2021).

However, there was a hasty adoption of this blend of online, broadcast, and other learning delivery modalities. Moreover, the development of curricula and other learning resources was likewise made abruptly without much thought on potential risks in students’ outcomes. This led to some discrepancies in students’ learning, particularly in their reading performance in English. Reading performance refers to the students’ ability to extract relevant information from narrative and informational texts and to understand, use, and reflect on written texts in areas of life that are relevant to the individual and required by society. It also involves multiple levels of text comprehension in terms of surface structure, pragmatic communication, text base, situation model, and rhetorical structure. A student has a good performance in reading if they have mastered text comprehension along with word recognition, such as decoding skills, language comprehension in terms of verbal reasoning, and the bridging processes, such as vocabulary knowledge (Duke & Cartwright, 2021).

Even prior to the onslaught of the COVID-19 pandemic, Filipino 15-year-old students already showed performance in reading based on the results of the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) where they scored an average point of 340, which was more than 200 points below the average reading score of China at 555 and more than 100 points less than the average reading score of 487 by the OECD. Hence, the country had placed 79th among the member countries in its ranking in the reading domain. There were differential effects in the students’ reading performance that were brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic. In the 2022 PISA, the Filipino students scored an average of 347 points in reading, which was still below the OECD average score of 476 points. Although there was a slight increase in the reading score for at most seven points from the 340 score in 2018 to 347 score in 2022, this is an insignificant increase that shows significant learning losses equivalent to an average of five to six years’ worth of schooling (Chi, 2023).

Similarly, the students’ oral reading performance, as evidenced by the results of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI), presented diminishing efficiency in reading skills at the primary grade levels. This diminishing efficiency was extended in

later years, as shown in the survey, where only 6.59 percent of the high school students could read, speak, and understand English, whereas 44.25 percent did not know the English language at all. These assessment results in both local and international reading assessments of Filipino students reflected the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on students' reading performance. As a result, the poor reading performance of the students indicated the less-than-optimum efficacy of the blended learning modality during the COVID-19 pandemic. The lack of social interaction between the teachers and the students when learning face-to-face and the lack of an authentic classroom environment led to the ineffectiveness of the blended learning approach to improve students' reading performance (Tong et al., 2022).

The inability of the blended learning approach to fill the gaps in reading of the students led to the question of its generalizability to students at the primary grade levels, specifically those in Grade 4, in rural public schools, such as those in the District of Tarangan, Schools Division of Samar. Based on the PHIL-IRI results during the School Year 2021-2022, the District of Tarangan, Schools Division of Samar, had a total of 34 non-readers, 56 frustration level readers, and 33 students at the independent level out of the 124 total Grade 4 population. Moreover, results from the Progress Monitoring and Evaluation Data Sheet from the First Quarter of the School Year 2022-2023 were shown during the District Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adjustment in the District Office of Tarangan. These results in reading implied dismal reading performance among Grade 4 students, which necessitate school interventions. On this premise, the researcher was motivated to conduct this study, which determined the potential relationship between the utilization of the blended learning approach and the Grade 4 students' reading performance in the District of Tarangan, Schools Division of Samar, to provide insights and research-based perspectives on reading policy formulation.

Research Questions

This study determined the relationship between the blended learning approach and reading performance of the Grade 4 students in the District of Tarangan, Schools Division of Samar, during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the student-respondents in terms of the following variates:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 parents' highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4 parents' occupation status;
 - 1.5 gross monthly family income;
 - 1.6 nutritional status;
 - 1.7 number of available reading materials at home; and
 - 1.8 attitude toward schooling?
2. What is the reading performance of the student-respondents in the following subject areas:

- 2.1 Filipino; and
- 2.2 English?
3. What is the reading performance level of the student-respondents in the blended learning modality along the following aspects:
 - 3.1 comprehension level;
 - 3.2 reading level; and
 - 3.3 speed level?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the reading performance in two subject areas of the student-respondents and the following variates:
 - 4.1 student-related variates; and
 - 4.2 reading performance level in blended learning modality?
5. What intervention program may be derived from the findings of this study?

Locale of the Study

Figure 1 presents the map of the locale of the study, the public elementary schools in the District of Tarangnan, Schools Division of Samar.

The study was conducted in the District of Tarangnan, Schools Division of Samar, involving its different elementary schools, namely: Balugo Elementary School (ES), Bangon ES, Baras ES, Binalayan ES, Bonga ES, Cabunga-an ES, Cagtutulo ES, Cambatutay Nuevo ES, Cambatutay Viejo ES, Canunghan ES, Dapdap ES, Gallego ES, Lahong ES, Libucan Dacu ES, Libucan Gote ES, Lucerdoni ES, Majacob Integrated School, Mancares ES, Oeste ES, Pajo ES, Palencia ES, San Vicente ES, Sta. Cruz ES, Sto. Nino ES, Tarangnan Central School, Tigdaranao ES, and Tizon ES.

During the earlier part of the 17th Century, Tarangnan, or Tinago was the first settlement of Jesuit missionaries in the Island of Samar. Tinago was considered the first cabecera in Samar, where the first Jesuits arrived, on October 15, 1596. When Tinago was devastated by the Moro attack in 1616, the Jesuits decided to transfer the cabecera to Catbalogan. Since that time, Tinago had not come back to life as a pueblo until 1725. The population was established at Dapdap, but for access and sanitation, it was moved to Tarangnan in 1883–1884. The attempted move of the pueblo from Dapdap to Tarangnan in 1882 became a highly celebrated case. It was a struggle or a fight between the parish priest of Dapdap, Fr. Angel Pulido, OFM, and the gobernadorcillo of Dapdap. The town of Dapdap was transferred in 1884 to a barrio called Tarangnan, from which it derives its name today. At first, the church and convento were constructed of light materials, which were bamboo and nipa. The new church was constructed in 1894 by P. Venancio Palencia, OFM, and completed in 1897. In the second half of the 19th Century, the island of Samar experienced a commercial boom, especially in abaca.

Figure 1

The Map Showing the Locale of the Study

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a quantitative approach using a descriptive-correlational research design to determine the relationship between the blended learning approach and the reading performance of Grade 4 students in the District of Tarangnan, Schools Division of Samar, during School Year 2022–2023. A total of 266 student-respondents were selected from 344 Grade 4 pupils through stratified random sampling using Slovin's formula. Data were gathered using a standardized questionnaire that measured students' profile variables and attitude toward schooling, and the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI) in Filipino and English to assess reading performance in terms of comprehension, reading level, and speed. The instruments were content-validated by experts. Data collection was conducted personally by the researcher with prior approval from education authorities. The collected data were analyzed using appropriate descriptive and inferential statistical tools, including frequency count, percentage, median, mean absolute deviation, weighted mean, chi-square test, Cramer's V, Spearman's rank correlation, Fisher's t-test, and probability value, with a 0.05 level of significance, to describe variables and determine significant relationships among them.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following were the salient findings of the study:

1. The median age is 10 years with a moderate Mean Absolute Deviation of 1.7 years, showing variability around the mean, while the majority of individuals are aged 9 and 10, emphasizing a concentration in these age groups. Additionally, the study highlights a higher representation of female students at 58.27 percent compared to male students at 41.73 percent.
2. The largest group of student-respondents have parents who are high school graduates (28.95 percent), followed by college graduates (19.17 percent) and elementary graduates (20.30 percent). A smaller proportion have parents with higher educational levels.
3. Only 18.42 percent of student-respondents have employed parents, while 81.58 percent have unemployed parents.
4. The student-respondents come from lower-income families, with 34.59 percent falling in the Php 1,000.00 - Php 5,000.00 range. Notably, the mode income bracket is Php 10,000.00.
5. Majority of the student-respondent, 96.99 percent, have a normal nutritional status, indicating overall satisfactory well-being, while 3.01 percent are classified as "wasted".

6. The majority of student-respondents (88.35 percent) have access to books at home, indicating ample reading opportunities, while a significant proportion (67.67 percent) have dictionaries for language development. Other reading materials like magazines, newspapers, encyclopedias, and novels are less common in students' homes.

7. The grand weighted mean of 4.16 suggests that students have a positive attitude towards reading and learning, with strong agreement on statements like "I enjoy reading stories" (4.32) and "Reading is one of the best ways for me to learn new things" (4.26).

8. The student-respondents' reading performance in Filipino indicates a majority (52.63 percent) scoring within the 16-20 range, with a median score of 15, reflecting strong proficiency.

9. The student-respondents' reading performance in English reveals a majority (51.88 percent) scoring within the 15-19 range, with a median score of 15, indicating strong proficiency.

10. The student-respondents demonstrated strong reading comprehension skills with a grand weighted mean of 3.65. Their performance in the blended learning program indicated a "Very Good" level of reading proficiency. In terms of reading speed, students achieved a "Very Good" level with a grand weighted mean of 3.63. The findings suggest that blended learning effectively enhanced students' reading fluency, accuracy, and comprehension.

11. The study revealed that parents' highest educational attainment significantly influences students' reading performance, emphasizing the impact of parental education on academic outcomes. In contrast, parents' occupation, gross monthly family income, nutritional status, and the availability of reading material at home showed no significant association with reading performance. Additionally, students' attitudes toward schooling were found to have a notable influence on their reading performance.

12. The study found a significant relationship between student reading performance and reading proficiency in a blended learning setting, with a low but statistically significant correlation coefficient of 0.197.

Conclusions

From the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The student-respondents has relatively uniform age distribution, with a slight majority of female students compared to male students.

2. The student-respondents have parents with varying educational backgrounds, with high school graduates being the most common, emphasizing the need for tailored support strategies to address the diverse academic needs of students.

3. The majority of student-respondents have unemployed parents, indicating a significant socioeconomic challenge that may impact their academic performance and overall well-being.

4. The student-respondents predominantly come from lower-income families, indicating a potential financial constraint that may impact the students' educational experiences and outcomes.

5. The majority of student-respondents exhibit a normal nutritional status, suggesting overall satisfactory well-being. However, a notable proportion are classified as "wasted," indicating a potential health concern that may impact their academic performance and overall quality of life.

6. The majority of student-respondents have access to books at home, indicating ample reading opportunities.

7. The students exhibit a positive attitude toward reading and learning, strongly agreeing with statements about enjoying reading and recognizing it as an effective way to learn new things.

8. The student-respondents demonstrate strong proficiency in reading performance in Filipino and English, with the majority scoring within the upper range.

9. The blended learning program effectively enhanced the students' reading fluency, accuracy, and comprehension, with their performance indicating a "Very Good" level of reading proficiency.

10. The parents' educational attainment significantly influences students' reading performance, emphasizing the impact of parental education on academic outcomes. However, other factors like parents' occupation, family income, nutritional status, and availability of reading materials at home showed no significant association with reading performance. Additionally, students' attitudes toward schooling were found to have a notable influence on their reading performance.

11. There is a significant relationship between student reading performance and reading proficiency in a blended learning setting, indicating that the blended learning approach positively impacts students' reading abilities.

Recommendations

Anchored on the conclusions drawn from the findings, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Implement targeted support programs to address the diverse academic needs of students, especially those from lower-income families and with unemployed parents.

2. Enhance efforts to improve nutritional status among students to support their

overall well-being and academic performance.

3. Ensure equitable access to reading materials at home to further promote reading opportunities and literacy development.

4. Continue leveraging blended learning approaches to enhance students' reading proficiency and overall academic success.

5. Provide additional support for students based on their parents' educational background to optimize academic outcomes.

6. Foster a positive attitude towards learning and reading among students to further enhance their academic engagement and performance.

7. Another study may be conducted to validate the findings of this study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to established ethical standards in educational research. Prior to data collection, formal approval was obtained from the Schools Division Superintendent, District Supervisor, and school heads concerned. Participation of the Grade 4 student-respondents was voluntary, and informed consent was secured through proper coordination with school authorities, teachers, and parents or guardians. The respondents were adequately informed of the purpose of the study and were assured that their participation would not pose any physical, psychological, or academic risks. Confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents were strictly maintained, and all data gathered were used solely for academic and research purposes. The results were reported honestly and objectively, ensuring respect for the rights, welfare, and dignity of all participants throughout the conduct of the study.

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